

A study to assess the knowledge regarding impact of excessive use of mobile phone with internet among mothers of adolescent age group in selected urban area of Udupi with a view to develop information booklet

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Abstract

Descriptive research designs with descriptive survey approach were used to evaluate the knowledge regarding Impact of excessive use of mobile phone with internet among mothers of adolescent age group in selected urban area of Udupi District. view of nature of the problem and accomplish the objectives of the study, a structured self administered knowledge questionnaire was prepared to assess the knowledge of mothers of adolescent age group in selected urban area and later the informational booklet was given. Reliability of the tool was tested and validity was ensured in consultation with guides and experts in field of Nursing and Medicine. The study was conducted in Kaup Urban area, Udupi. 100 mothers were selected by purposive sampling technique. Structured knowledge questionnaire was used to collect the data. Collected data was analyzed by using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Results: The present study revealed that the mean obtained for Overall knowledge scores of mothers 72 (72%) subjects had poor knowledge level and 28 (28%) subjects had moderate knowledge on impact of excessive use of mobile with internet. Area-wise analysis of Knowledge of mothers regarding impact of excessive use of mobile with internet shows that the mean percentages of overall knowledge obtained by the respondents are 46.5 percent with a SD of 7.17. Only educational status variable had significant association with knowledge scores and other variables didn't had any association. So, research hypothesis is accepted only for educational status and null hypothesis is accepted for other variables like age, religion, family income, occupation, husband occupation, number of children, previous information and source of information.

Interpretation and conclusion The study revealed that majority of mothers had lack of knowledge regarding impact of excessive use of mobile phone with internet. Hence there is a need to improve knowledge of the regarding Impact of excessive use of mobile phone with internet through informational booklet. There was statistically significant association found between knowledge score and educational status variables.

Keywords: Knowledge; Informational booklet; Impact of excessive use of mobile; Internet

1. Introduction

Human being is a social animal. To socialize with others, we need to share over views, beliefs, feelings etc. This sharing is facilitated by communication. Communication is the transfer of information from person to person. This may be in form of sound transmission such as human speech, the beating of the drum, or eventhe bird's call. It can also be in a form that requires sight like writing, pictures, and signals, gestures and a form that requires the utilization of other senses. There are many means on how you can reach out to other people to communicate and one of this is the use of a mobile cell phone. It can be used for business calls that binds twoor group of people to convey messages to each other and these

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are possibly made for colleagues and business men or employers to conduct business and meetings anytime, anywhere.¹ Mobile phone is a small, portable communication device that enables people to make phone calls whenever where they are. Signal transmission is the very basic concept for mobile phone. The convenience of mobile phone is allowing people to communicate with one another without the limitation of regions and time. Mobile phone is a device providing two-way communication. The technology influencing on mobile phone started back in the mid twentieth century.² The concept of mobile phone was invented during the Second World War by the American Dr. Martin cooper in April 1973 at New York. Mobile phones were invented because people wanted to communicate faster and at different locations.³ A Mobile phone is a must have item for many an average teenager. Many people spend more than six hours a day on their phones in talking, texting or playing games. The extensive use of cell phone is making us addict of this small device. Just like every medicine has its side effects, cell phones also have some drawbacks. The increased usage of mobile phone has increased the magnitude of potential health risks among its users.⁴ The mobile phone could be the most incredible device ever made in the consumer world. The mobile phone which started as a bulky device for voice communication has in the last 15 years, morphed into lean models with a bewildering array of features. However, among the billion plus consumers worldwide, the prime utility of the mobile phone remains voice.⁵

2. Material and methods

2.1. Research Approach

Research approach is a basic procedure for conducting the research study.⁵⁹ In the present study a survey approach was used to assess the knowledge regarding impact of excessive use of mobile phone with internet among mothers of adolescent age group.

2.2. Research Design

A research design is a blueprint for conducting the study that maximizes control over factors that could interfere with the validity of the findings. The research design guides the researcher in planning and implementing the study in a way that is most likely to achieve the intended goal. Descriptive design has been adopted for the present study.

2.3. Setting of the Study

The present study was conducted in Kaup, Udipi district, it is 17 km away from the college. Due to the geographical proximity, feasibility of the study and availability of the samples Kaup area was selected for the study.

2.4. Population

In the present study the target population comprises of 100 mothers of adolescents age group residing at Kaup, Udipi district.

2.5. Sample and Sample Size

In the present study the sample comprises of 100 mothers of adolescents who fulfilled the inclusion criteria for the study.

2.6. Sampling Technique

Purposive sampling technique was found to be appropriate for the present study.

2.7. Data collection Technique

Methods of data collection include development of tool, testing of validity and reliability and data collection procedure. The instruments selected in research should be as far as possible the vehicles that would best obtain data for drawing conclusion which are pertinent for the study. A structured knowledge questionnaire on impact of mobile phone was used for data collection.

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2.9. Plan for Data Analysis

- Data would be arranged in a master sheet
- The computed data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics on the basis of objectives and hypothesis of study
- The knowledge of the mother would be analyzed using frequency and percentage. The same will be presented using bar diagram.
- Association between knowledge score and selected baseline characteristics would be analyzed by Chi-square test.
- The data would be presented in the form of tables and figures.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Presentation of data

To begin with, the data was entered in a master sheet for tabulation and statistical processing. The data is analyzed and interpreted using descriptive and inferential statistics. The data is presented under the following headings.

- Section I

This section deals with the demographic characteristics of the sample.

- Section II

This section deals with the knowledge scores of the participants on impact of excessive use of mobile phone with internet

- Part A: Overall knowledge scores of mothers regarding Impact of excessive use of mobile phone with internet
- Part B: Area wise knowledge scores of subjects according to their knowledge level.

- Section III

This section deals with the findings related to association between knowledge and selected demographic variables of the study.

3.1.1. Section I

Demographic characteristics of the respondents

Table 1 Distribution of mothers based on their demographic characteristics N=100

S.N	Demographic variables	Options	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Age in years	26-30	7	7%
		31-35	26	26%
		36-40	35	35%
		41-45	22	22%
		Above 46	10	10%
2.	Educational status	No formal education	19	19%
		Primary education	11	11%
		Secondary education	10	10%
		PUC	52	52%
		Degree and above	8	8%
3.	Religion	Hindu	89	89%
		Muslim	6	6%

		Christian	5	5%
		Any other	-	-
4.	Family income	Below Rs 10,000/-	45	45%
		Rs 10,001-15,000	13	13%
		Rs 15,001-20,000	23	23%
		Above Rs 20,001	19	19%
5.	Occupation	Housewife	39	39%
		Government employee	32	32%
		Private employee	26	26%
		Self employed	3	3%
6.	Husband occupation	Government employee	57	57%
		Private employee	28	28%
		Other	15	15%
7.	Number of children	One	34	34%
		Two	49	49%
		Three	11	11%
		Four and above	6	6%
8.	Previous information	Yes	10	10%
		No	90	90%
9.	Source of information	Health personnel	-	-
		Family members	-	-
		Friends	-	-
		Mass media	10	10%
		None	90	90%

3.1.2. Section II

Assessment of pretest and post test level of knowledge of mothers regarding impact of excessive use of mobile with internet.

Table 2 Distribution of subject's overall knowledge scores N=100

Overall knowledge of subjects	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Poor	72	72%
Moderate	28	28%
Good	0	0%
Excellent	0	0%
Total	100	100%

According to Table 2, majority 72 (72%) subjects had poor knowledge level and 28 (28%) subjects had moderate knowledge on impact of excessive use of mobile with internet.

Table 3 Area wise knowledge scores of respondents on impact of excessive use of mobile with internet N=100

Area	No. of question	mean	Mean%	SD
Introduction	1	0.42	42	0.37
Incidence	1	0.44	44	0.48
Mobile with internet	1	0.41	41	0.36
Advantages	2	0.43	43	0.34
Disadvantages	2	1.26	42	0.54
Mechanism of mobile	1	2.4	42.4	0.85
Negative effects of mobile	15	8.68	44.3	3.73
Precautions	7	3.28	43	0.5
Total	30	14.1	46.5	7.17

Table.3: reveals that the maximum mean percent obtained by the respondents is 44.3% with SD of 03.73 in the area of negative effects of mobile and the minimum mean percent obtained by the respondents is 41 with a SD Of 0.36 in the aspect of mobile with internet. The mean percentages of overall knowledge obtained by the respondents are 46.5 percent with a SD of 7.17.

3.1.3. Section III

Table 4 Association between knowledge score and selected demographic variables N=100

S. N	Variables	Options	Knowledge scores		χ^2
			< median	≥median	
1.	Age in years	26-30	5	2	0.9 NS
		31-35	20	6	
		36-40	31	4	
		41-45	19	3	
		Above 46	8	2	
2	Educational status	No formal education	15	4	15.23*S
		Primary education	10	1	
		Secondary education	8	2	
		PUC	48	4	
		Degree and above	7	1	
3	Religion	Hindu	75	14	1.77 NS
		Muslim	5	1	
		Christian	3	2	
		Any other	-	-	
4	Income	Below Rs 10,000/-	40	5	1.37 NS
		Rs 10,001-15,000	12	1	
		Rs 15,001-20,000	18	5	
		Above Rs 20,001	11	8	

5	Occupation	Housewife	36	3	0.0049 NS
		Government employee	28	4	
		Private employee	21	5	
		Self employed	2	1	
6	Husband occupation	Government employee	49	8	0.53 NS
		Private employee	19	9	
		Other	10	5	
		One	26	8	0.0051NS
7	No of children	Two	41	8	
		Three	9	2	
		Four and above	4	2	
8	Previous info	Yes	5	5	0.62 NS
		No	70	20	
9	Source of info	Health personnel	-	-	0.92 NS
		Family members	-	-	
		Friends	-	-	
		Mass media	5	5	
		None	70	20	

NS- Nothing significant; *S- Significant

The above table depicts association between knowledge score and selected demographic variables. In that only educational status had significant association with knowledge scores and other variables didn't had any association. So, the Chi square result established there is significant association between knowledge level of respondents and educational status. So, research hypothesis is accepted only for educational status and null hypothesis is accepted for other variables like age, religion, family income, occupation, husband occupation, number of children, previous information and source of information.

4. Conclusion

This chapter deals with the conclusion, implications, recommendations and limitations of the study "A study to assess the knowledge regarding impact of excessive use of mobile phone with internet among mothers of adolescent age group in selected urban area of Udupi with a view to develop information booklet"

The following conclusions can be drawn on the basis of the findings.

- **Age:** In the present study it was found that the majority of the respondents 35 % (35) belongs to the age group of 36-40 years, 26% (26) respondents to the age group of 31-35 years, 22% (22) respondents to the age group of 41-45 years, 10% (10) respondents to the age group of above 46 years and 7% (7) to 26-30 years.
- **Educational status:** In the present study it was found that the majority of respondents 52% (52) are PUC, 19% (19) are no formal education, 11% (11) are primary education, 10% (10) are secondary education and only 8% (8) are degree and above.
- **Religion:** In the present study it was found that the among the respondents 89% (29) were Hindu, 6% (6) were Muslim and 5% (5) were Christian.
- **Family income:** In the present study it was found that the 45% (45) had below Rs 10,000/-, 23% (23) had Rs 15,001-20,000/-, 19% (19) had above 20,001/- and 13% (13) had Rs 10,001-15,000/-.
- **Occupation:** In the present study it was found that the majority 39% (39) were housewife, 32% (32) were government employee, 26% (26) were private employee and 3% (3) were self-employed.
- **Husband occupation:** In the present study it was found that the 57% (57) were government employee, 28% (28) were private employees and 15% (15) were having others occupation like business, daily wages etc.

- **Number of children:** In the present study it was found that the 49% (49) had two children, 34% (34) had one child, 11%(11) had three children and 6% (6) had four and above children.
- **Previous information:** In the present study it was found that the 90% (90) had no previous information regarding impact of mobile phone with internet and 10% (10) had previous information a regarding impact of mobile phone with internet.
- **Source of information:** In the present study it was found that the 90% (40) had no source of information and only 10% (10) had information through mass media.

In the present study with respect to overall knowledge score it was found that the majority 72 (72%) subjects had poor knowledge level and 28 (28%) subjects had moderate knowledge on impact of excessive use of mobile with internet

Area-wise analysis of Knowledge of mothers regarding impact of excessive use of mobile with internet shows that the maximum mean percent obtained by the respondents is 44.3% with SD of 03.73 in the area of negative effects of mobile and the minimum mean percent obtained by the respondents is 41 with a SD Of 0.36 in the aspect of mobile with internet. The mean percentages of overall knowledge obtained by the respondents are 46.5 percent with a SD of 7.17.

Only educational status variable had significant association with knowledge scores and other variables didn't had any association. So, the Chi square result established there is significant association between knowledge level of respondents and educational status. So, research hypothesis is accepted only for educational status and null hypothesis is accepted for other variables like age, religion, family income, occupation, husband occupation, number of children, previous information and source of information.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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